

Synthesis and physicochemical studies of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with 2-acetyl thiophene thiosemicarbazone (L)

Sulekh Chandra* and Anil Kumar

Department of Chemistry, Zakir Husain College, J. L. N. Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail : schandra_00@yahoo.com; anil_sharma957@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were synthesized with thiosemicarbazone (L) derived from 2-acetyl thiophene. These complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, mass, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies. The molar conductance measurement of the complexes in DMSO indicates that the complexes are non-electrolyte. All the complexes are of high-spin type. On the basis of spectral studies an octahedral geometry may be assigned for Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes whereas tetragonal for Cu^{II} complexes.

Keywords : Thiosemicarbazone, copper(II), manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II).

Thiosemicarbazones and their complexes have received considerable attention because of their pharmacological activities¹. Thiosemicarbazones react with metals giving complexes in which the ligand behaves as chelating agent coordinating through the sulphur and the hydrazine nitrogen atoms. In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with 2-acetyl thiophene thiosemicarbazone (L).

Structure of ligand (L)

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade (Sigma Aldrich). Metal salts were used as received. All solvents used were of standard/spectroscopic grade.

Preparation of ligand (L) and metal complexes : The ligand (L) was prepared as reported earlier². Hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding metal salt (0.005 mol) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol). The reaction was carried out at pH ~6.5. The mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h on a water bath. On cooling to 0°C, a colored complex separated out in each case. The same was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Purity of the complexes was checked by TLC.

Hot aqueous solution (20 mL) of metal salt MnSO₄·H₂O (0.005 mol) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol) in molar ratio 1 : 2. The reaction was carried out at pH ~6.5. The mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h on a water bath. On cooling to 0°C, a colored complex separated out. The same was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Purity of the complex was checked by TLC.

Physical measurement : The C, H, N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the Elico (CM82T) conducting bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as a calibrant. Mass spectra were recorded on JEOL, JMS.DX-303 mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample at LNT for Co^{II} complexes and at room temperature for Cu^{II} complexes on E4-EPR spectrometer using DPPH as the g-marker.

Results and discussion

The IR spectrum of ligand (L) shows bands at 3380 and 3171 cm⁻¹ which may be, assigned to -NH₂ and -NH groups respectively. The bands due to ν(C=S) and ν(C=N) groups appeared at 817 and 1597 cm⁻¹. The mass spectrum of free ligand (L) confirms the proposed formula by showing a peak at 200 amu corresponding to the molecular ion (M⁺¹) C₇H₉N₃S₂. It also shows a peak indicating the loss of (-CSNH₂) i.e. at 140 amu and various other fragments.

Table 1. Elemental analysis and molar conductance data of complexes

Complex	Mol. cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Color	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					M	C	H	N
Mn(L) ₂ Cl ₂	15.2	Violet	195	62	10.28 (10.48)	41.20 (41.44)	3.25 (3.43)	16.30 (16.03)
Mn(L) ₂ SO ₄	11.5	Red	185	50	10.26 (10.01)	30.27 (30.60)	3.52 (3.27)	15.05 (15.30)
Co(L) ₂ Cl ₂	15	Dark brown	188	66	11.40 (11.16)	31.58 (31.82)	3.17 (3.40)	15.71 (15.91)
Co(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	10	Rose pink	182	61	10.37 (10.14)	28.68 (28.91)	3.34 (3.09)	19.03 (19.27)
Ni(L) ₂ Cl ₂	10	Green	187	65	11.36 (11.12)	40.70 (40.93)	3.64 (3.48)	15.67 (15.91)
Ni(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	15	Magenta	185	67	10.36 (10.11)	37.33 (37.19)	3.34 (3.09)	19.50 (19.28)
Cu(L) ₂ Cl ₂	23	Green	190	61	11.72 (11.93)	31.32 (31.54)	3.13 (3.38)	15.53 (15.77)
Cu(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	19	Brown	185	66	10.67 (10.85)	28.51 (28.69)	3.32 (3.07)	19.36 (19.12)

On complexation the bands corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ are shifted towards lower side (*ca.* 20–30 cm^{-1}). This suggests that the ligand acts as a bidentate chelating agent coordinating through nitrogen of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group and sulphur of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ group.

On the basis of elemental analysis the complexes were found to have the composition as shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO indicate that the complexes are non-electrolyte³. Thus the complexes may be formulated as $[\text{M}(\text{L})_2\text{X}_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, NO_3^- and $1/2 \text{SO}_4^{2-}$. IR spectrum of sulphate complex of Mn^{II} shows bands at 1108, 1059 and 1029 cm^{-1} indicates that the sulphate group coordinated to metal ion as bidentate. IR spectra of nitrate complexes display three absorption bands in the range 1415–1440, 1290–1315 and 1020–1050 cm^{-1} suggesting that both the nitrate groups are coordinated to the metal ion⁴.

The magnetic moment values of all the complexes are given in Table 2. Electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes display weak absorption bands in the range 16925–18330, 21000–23000, 26660–29325, 33725–35115 cm^{-1} (Table 2) characteristic to octahedral geometry. These bands may be assigned as ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g} ({}^4\text{G}) (10\text{B} + 5\text{C})$, ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}_g$, ${}^4\text{A}_{1g} ({}^4\text{G}) (10\text{B} + 5\text{C})$, ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}_g ({}^4\text{D}) (17\text{B} + 5\text{C})$ and ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g} ({}^4\text{P}) (7\text{B} + 7\text{C})$ transitions respectively⁵. The experimentally⁵ observed transition energies and calculated values for parameter B , C , Dq and β are given in Table 3. The values for parameters B and C could be obtained using transition ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}_g$, ${}^4\text{A}_{1g} ({}^4\text{G})$ and ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}_g ({}^4\text{D})$. This is due to the fact that energies of these two transitions are independent of the crystal field splitting energy and depend only on the parameter B and C ⁶. The value for parameters Dq could be evaluated with help of curve transition energies vs Dq given by Orgel⁷ using the energy level due to transition

Table 2. Magnetic moment and electronic spectral data of complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectral data (cm^{-1})			
		ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	ν_4
Mn(L) ₂ Cl ₂	5.92	17700	21270	28550	34420
Mn(L) ₂ SO ₄	5.95	17275	21000	28300	34010
Co(L) ₂ Cl ₂	4.80	9420	14525	18975	–
Co(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	4.83	9325	14450	18775	–
Ni(L) ₂ Cl ₂	2.97	9680	16200	24500	–
Ni(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.93	9650	15250	24600	–
Cu(L) ₂ Cl ₂	2.06	14580	16675	–	–
Cu(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.03	13214	16540	–	–

Table 3. Ligand field parameters and *g* value of complexes

Complex	<i>g</i>	LFSE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	<i>Dq</i> (cm ⁻¹)	β	<i>B</i> (cm ⁻¹)
Mn(L) ₂ Cl ₂	1.75	–	1770	0.59	468
Mn(L) ₂ SO ₄	1.85	–	1727	0.59	471
Co(L) ₂ Cl ₂	1.79	135	942	0.55	–
Co(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1.89	133	932	0.54	–
Ni(L) ₂ Cl ₂	–	139	968	0.74	–
Ni(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	–	138	965	0.69	–
Cu(L) ₂ Cl ₂	2.00	–	–	–	–
Cu(L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1.97	–	–	–	–

${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$. Parameters *B* and *C* are linear combinations of certain Coulomb and exchange integral are generally treated as empirical parameter obtained from the spectra of the free ions. The EPR spectra of the complexes have been recorded as polycrystalline samples. All the complexes give one broad isotropic signal. The *g* values have been calculated and given in Table 3. The *g* values are almost equal to free electron *g* value (i.e. 2.0023). Co^{II} complexes show three electronic spectral bands in the range 7000–10000 and 14000–17000 and 18000–22000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the following transitions ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F)$, ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (F)$, ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$.

The 4F state of *d*⁷ in an octahedral crystal field is split into three states. Since these states are connected by the spin orbit coupling the spin lattice relaxation times are short making EPR measurements possible only at very low temperature. EPR spectra of the complexes recorded as polycrystalline sample at liquid nitrogen temperature and *g* values are given in Table 3. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show bands in the range 8580–13000, 11000–20000 and 19000–27000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to spin allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g} (F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} (F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} (P) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$ indicate an octahedral geometry. These Cu^{II} complexes under study display electronic spectral bands in the range 13000–16000 and 16000–20000 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned⁸ to the following transition in order of increasing energy ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$. EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample on X-band at frequency 9.5 GHz under the magnetic field strength 3400 Gauss. All the complexes show anisotropic EPR spectra⁹. The *g* value have been calculated by Kivelson's method¹⁰. $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, which measures the exchange interaction between copper centers in the polycrystalline solid.

The value of *Dq* in Co^{II} complexes were calculated from transition energy ratio diagram using the ν_3/ν_2 ratio⁵. The Nephelauxetic parameter β was readily obtained by using the relation $\beta = B(\text{complex})/B(\text{free ion})$, where *B* free ion for Mn^{II} is 786 cm⁻¹ for Ni^{II} is 1041 cm⁻¹ and for Co^{II} is 1120 cm⁻¹

(Ref. 11). The value of β lies in the range 0.54–0.74 (Table 3). These values indicate the appreciable covalent character of metal ligand σ bond. On the basis of spectral studies the following structure may be suggested for the complexes.

where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}

Suggested structure for the complexes

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